

UTILIZATION OF SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL IN DEVELOPING LEARNING COMPETENCIES IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP AMONG GRADE 9 STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 4

Pages: 447-456

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2067

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12778753

Manuscript Accepted: 06-13-2024

Utilization of Supplementary Material in Developing Learning Competencies in Entrepreneurship among Grade 9 Students

Janen C. Galang*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The availability of printed learning materials in teaching Entrepreneurship 9 is one of the issues that require immediate attention to address the needs of grade 9 students and make their lessons more understandable. The study utilized Supplementary Material in Developing Competencies in Entrepreneurship among grade 9 and determined the perception of the learners on the components of the learning material. Descriptive-correlational research design was employed, involving the 95 grade 9 students. The statistical tools used were Frequency and Percentage, Mean and SD, and Pearson correlation coefficient to measure the students' perception in the Supplementary Material and determine the relationships between Supplementary Materials and competencies in Entrepreneurship among grade 9 students. The findings of the study revealed that most of the respondents were 14 years old and mostly were female. Students perceived the learning materials positively, strongly agreeing that the materials had clear learning objectives, instructions, and examples, and that the key points and arguments were logically presented. They also agreed that the materials were well-organized, with proper spacing, readable fonts, and covered the key concepts. However, the perception of the learners on the components of learning materials was significantly related to developed supplementary materials. Meanwhile, the components of learning materials to oral presentation were not significantly related. The study concludes that while developed learning materials were effective in enhancing business planning skills, their impact on oral presentation skills is less significant. The hypothesis that learning material components are not significantly related to learning competencies in entrepreneurship was not sustained. Tests revealed no significant association between respondents' performance in oral presentations and their perception of learning material objectives ($r = 0.075$), content evaluation ($r = 0.144$), and learning reflection ($r = 0.166$). However, low correlations were found between oral presentation competency and components of learning materials such as topics ($r = 0.286^{**}$), pedagogy ($r = 0.236^{**}$), layout ($r = 0.221^*$), adaptability ($r = 0.303^{**}$), and user-friendliness ($r = 0.273^{**}$). Factors such as the nature of oral presentations and the complexity of learning outcomes may influence these results. This finding aligns with Park and Kim (2021), who emphasizes that user-friendly design in online learning materials fosters better business planning skills. Enhancing curriculum design and learning materials could improve student performance and satisfaction.

Keywords: *supplementary material, competencies in entrepreneurship, components of learning materials*

Introduction

One of the most essential resources and the first thing a teacher should offer are teaching materials, but to create one, a teacher must first have access to a reliable source. When putting together instructional materials, educators require access to trustworthy and current sources. These resources may include textbooks/modules, articles, research papers, academic journals, and MELCs provided by DepEd among others. Furthermore, the availability of these resources has evolved with the advent of digital technology. Teaching materials are considered crucial in any language program, as they provide learners with the necessary input and ideas to plan and teach lessons effectively in the classroom (Katawazai et al., 2019).

Moreover, from these resources, the educator must also be able to create supplemental learning materials that will apply to the needs of the learners which may be of help to arouse their interest in the topic that you want to teach them. Creating effective teaching materials is a crucial responsibility for educators, as these resources play a significant role in shaping students' learning experiences. Teaching materials serve as a guide and framework for teachers to structure their lessons and provide learners with the necessary input and practice opportunities. Research has shown that teaching materials, particularly textbooks, are reliable sources of ideas for inexperienced teachers and provide them with a working plan to outline the most appropriate approaches to teaching and learning various tasks. According to Richards, J. C. (2014), teaching materials act as a roadmap for teachers, helping them organize and deliver instruction systematically and effectively.

Furthermore, educators need to acknowledge and consider the diverse learning styles and abilities of their students when designing teaching materials. By creating differentiated and inclusive learning materials, educators can cater to the needs of all their learners and promote a more equitable classroom environment. In addition, educators must also ensure that the teaching materials align with the learning objectives and goals of the curriculum. This ensures that the materials are relevant and effective, promoting student engagement and academic success.

In connection with this Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) also has excellent educational objectives that align with MELCs. TLE aims to cultivate in students critical thinking, self-assurance, independence, cultural understanding, and business (DepEd, 2019).

It is accomplished through increasing their talents, skills, and capabilities in a variety of innovative applications and the use of essential skills. Because of this, it might be difficult for TLE teachers to implement teaching techniques that can effectively and efficiently make their message. Several teaching methods promote student-centeredness. K–12 kids have unique traits that should also be taken into consideration when developing online and printed learning tools. Today's students are highly adept at using the Internet to research topics, and they can also adjust well when their attention is focused on the example. This skill enables the student to move into various inclining situations, and they are also less likely to exhibit restraint in educational environments when they are not motivated or engaged (Simonson et al., 2012). As a result, as teachers, we ought to attempt to avoid using our printed foundational materials as a vehicle for disseminating information; instead, the information should be retained. The Department of Instruction has delivered the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) for use across the nation in response to the pandemic's challenges. Under some circumstances, this MELCS can be used as a component to ensure learning advancement. Additionally, it will enable the office to focus on coaching the most essential skills and competencies to students, while also addressing their individual needs and interests. To effectively implement the Most Essential Learning Competencies in Technology and Livelihood Education, teachers must consider various factors. First, teachers should ensure that they are thoroughly familiar with the MELCs and understand their purpose and objectives. This will enable them to align their teaching strategies and activities with the intended outcomes of the MELCs.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the association of the Supplementary Material in Developing Learning Competencies in Entrepreneurship among Grade 9 students. Specifically, the researcher sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents with regards to:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. family monthly income;
 - 1.4. parents' highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. parents' occupation?
2. How is the supplementary learning material be described as to components:
 - 2.1. contents;
 - 2.1.1. objectives;
 - 2.1.2. topics;
 - 2.1.3. pedagogy;
 - 2.1.4. evaluation;
 - 2.1.5. reflection;
 - 2.2. lay out;
 - 2.3. adaptive; and
 - 2.4. user Friendliness?
3. What is the level of students' learning competencies as to:
 - 3.1. develop a Business Plan; and
 - 3.2. oral Presentation?
4. Are the components of learning Material significantly related to:
 - 4.1. develop Business plan; and
 - 4.2. oral presentation of Business Plan?

Literature Review

Supplemental Learning Materials

The K-12 Law, officially known as Republic Act No. 10533, has significantly altered the Philippine educational system. With its need for two years of senior high school, four years of junior high school, and six years of primary education, the law highlights how crucial it is to have excellent teaching materials to assist with curriculum implementation. This involves offering more resources to improve the caliber of instruction and guarantee that pupils have a well-rounded education. The emphasis on enhancing instructional materials highlights the dedication to raising the bar for learning and getting pupils ready for success in the future.

Sec. 12 of DepEd Order No. 2020: This directive is sent to the Department of Education. (2020). Section 12 of DepEd Order No. 2020, which outlines the guidelines for the adoption and use of supplemental learning materials for the K–12 Basic Education Program, lays out the process for evaluating and choosing educational resources, including textbooks and supplemental materials, to ensure that they fulfill curriculum requirements and learning objectives. The purpose of these guidelines is to guarantee that students have access to excellent and suitable learning materials that support their academic goals and overall development.

Department of Education (2023). Sec. 24 of Policy Guidelines for Supplementary Instructional Materials Adoption and Use in Public Elementary and Secondary Schools, 2023. The policy guidelines for the adoption and use of supplemental teaching resources in public elementary and secondary schools are established by this order. It highlights how crucial it is to offer a variety of culturally appropriate

and varied resources to aid in the teaching and learning process. This policy acknowledges the need for additional teaching resources that address the wide range of learner requirements and backgrounds.

Solberg, Wills, Redmon, and Skaff's (2014) assessment tools are crucial in helping individuals identify potential interest areas and required skills for various occupations; individuals can gain a better understanding of the skills they possess and those they need to develop to pursue their desired careers. Accessible assessment tools can help individuals achieve their career goals and improve their overall quality of life. The development of personal qualities, often referred to as employability skills, is essential for success in the workforce which may include communication, teamwork, time management, problem-solving, adaptability, and leadership.

The development of self-determination skills is crucial for individuals to achieve their goals and lead fulfilling lives where individuals can take ownership of their lives and actively work towards their desired outcomes.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive-correlational research as this study intends to determine the relationship of supplementary material in developing competencies in Entrepreneurship among grade 9 students of Bondoc Peninsula Agricultural High School.

Respondents

The respondents of the study was randomly selected from four (4) sections of grade nine (9) students of Bondoc Peninsula Agricultural High School for the School Year 2023-2024. From those sections, the researcher also has randomly selected fifty percent (50%) of the population regardless if they are male or female as long as they belong to even numbers from the student's lists.

Instruments

The instrument used in this study in gathering data was a survey questionnaire made by the researcher. It is composed of several parts. Part I is the profile of the respondents, part 2 deals with the perception of respondents on the components of learning materials which includes contents (objectives, topics, pedagogy, evaluation and learning reflection) layout, adaptability and user-friendliness and part 3 was the perception of the respondents on the learning competencies in Entrepreneurship that includes developing a business plan and oral presentation. To ensure the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire it was subjected to internal and external validation from experts in the area of the study. Other measures employed in the validation process are incorporation of all the suggestions and comments of panel of experts during the proposal defense, conduct of pilot testing among the respondents, used of Cronbach's Alpha for likert questionnaire with the result of 0.94 and verbal interpretation of excellent. Furthermore, the supplementary material as the primary instrument in conducting the study was validated also by the expert in the field of TVE.

Procedure

The conceptualization and completion of this research underwent several phases: first was the development of supplementary learning materials and editing and validation of the Supplementary Material, second was seeking approval for the conduct of the study from the Department head, Principal, Dean of the college of Teacher Education –Graduate Studies and Applied Research as well as the panel members Administration of the research study Distribution and collection of the written and consent from the respondents, assuring them that all the data and information collected will be confidential, third was Data gathering procedure includes, Distributed Questionnaire to the target respondents and Recorded the data gathered from the questionnaire, and checked the collected output of the respondents with the used of rubrics to get the necessary data and fourth was for the statistical analysis which includes the accomplishment of data matrix which was submitted to the researcher's statistician and adviser for final review to ensure that the data needed were completely and correctly encoded in the data matrix to coincide with the statement of the problem raised in the study, and sending the approved data matrix together with the application form, survey questionnaire, statement of the problem and paradigm of the study to LSPU statistics Center for statistical treatment of data to answer the problems of the study.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in this study was subjected to the following statistical treatment.

Frequency and Percentage, were used to determine the profile of the respondents, Mean and SD to interpret the perception of the students in the Utilization of Supplementary Material In Developing Competencies In Entrepreneurship Among Grade 9 Students and the level of students competencies. On the other hand Pearson correlation coefficient–was used to determine the relationships between Supplemental Learning Materials and competencies in Business Plan among grade 9 Entrepreneurship students, testing its significance at the 0.05 level.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

The following table shows the distribution of the respondents' age, sex, family income, and parents' educational attainment.

Table 1 shows that out of Ninety five (95) respondents 67 or 70.53% belongs to 14 years old, twenty four (24) or 25.26% belongs to fifteen (15), three (3) or 3.16% belongs to the age 16 and one (1) or 1.1% belongs to seventeen (17) years old. It implies that the grade 9 students of Bondoc Peninsula Agricultural High School mostly were aged fourteen (14) and fifteen (15) and fewer of them were age 16 and 17. It is indicating that there is narrow age distribution within the grade.

With regards to the sex of the respondents, the data shows that the majorities of respondents were female with frequency of 65 or 68.42% while males' frequency are 30 or 31.58% of the total population. This implies that there is significant gender imbalance with more female students enrolled in grade 9 compare to male.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by Age, Sex, Family Income Parents' Highest Educational Attainment and Occupation*

Age	Profile	Frequency	Percentage	
	14	67	70.53	
	15	24	25.26	
	16	3	3.16	
	17	1	1.05	
Total		95	100	
Sex	Male	30	31.58	
	Female	65	68.42	
Total		95	100	
Family Monthly Income	5,000 Below	33	34.74	
	5,001-10,000	17	17.89	
	10,001-15,000	19	20	
	15,001-20,000	5	5.26	
	20,001-25,000	8	8.42	
	25,000 above	13	13.68	
Total		95	100	
Educational Attainment	Father		Mother	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Elementary Level	16	16.84	9	9.47
Elementary Graduate	10	10.53	10	10.53
High School Level	17	17.89	23	24.21
High School Graduate	26	27.37	27	28.42
College Level	11	11.58	12	12.63
College Graduate	12	12.63	13	13.68
Total		92	94	98.95
Deceased		3	1	1.05
Parents' Occupation	Employed	84	46	48.42
	Unemployed	9	48	50.53
Total		95	100	98.95
Deceased		2	1	1.05

The table also shows the family monthly income of the respondents, thirty three (33) or 34.74% of the respondents earned P 5,000 and below, seventeen (17) or 17.89% earns P 5,001-P 10,000, nineteen (19) or 20% are earning P 10,001-P15,000, five (5) or 5.26% earns P15,001-P20,000, eight (8) or 8.42% earns P20,001-P25,000 and thirteen (13) or 13.68% earns. This data shows a varied distribution of family income among the respondents. According to data, there are smaller percentage fall into higher income bracket and majority of the respondents' family earns smaller amount of money that the rests which may affect different aspects of their life including education.

Also, distribution of the respondents as to parents' educational background shows that the highest number of parents educational attainment with twenty six (26) or 27.37% were high school graduate, seventeen (17) or 17.89% were high school level, sixteen (16) or 16.84% were elementary level, twelve (12) or 12.63% were college graduate, eleven (11) or 11.58% were college level and ten (10) or 10.53% were elementary graduate. The statistical data shows that most of the fathers' highest educational attainments were high school graduate.

Similarly, mothers' educational attainment shows that twenty six(27) or 28.42% are high school graduate, followed by twenty three (23) or 24.21% high school level, thirteen (13) or 13.68% college graduate, twelve (12) or 12.63% college level, ten (10) or 10.53% elementary graduate and nine (9) or 9.47% were elementary Level. The statistical data revealed that both parents' educational background mostly falls within high school graduate category indicating that most of the respondents' parents have finished their secondary education and there are also smaller portion that falls into other educational background categories.

It also shows the respondents' parents occupation. Based on the table most of the fathers are employed since the fathers' employed

frequency is 84 or (88.82%), also 9 of them or (9.47%) are unemployed and 2 are deceased which is 2.11%. When it comes to their mother it is the opposite as it shows that most of them are unemployed with the frequency of 48 or (50.53%), employed are 46 or (48.42%) and 1 or (1.05%) of them is deceased. This data revealed a gender inequality in employment status with father mostly employed compared to mothers.

Table 2. *Perception of the respondents on the Contents of the Learning Materials as to Learning Objectives*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The Objectives of the learning materials</i>			
1. Helps in setting clear and achievable learning goals	3.58	0.69	Strongly Agree
2. Assists in defining my learning objectives	3.39	0.62	Agree
3. Are helpful in establishing specific milestones to achieve my learning goals	3.37	0.64	Agree
4. Is easy to understand	3.38	0.57	Agree
5. Has clear instructions/directions	3.60	0.53	Strongly Agree
6. Provides examples to clarify statement	3.64	0.48	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.54	0.53	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Table 2 shows the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials as to learning objectives. Based on the table, objectives has an overall mean of 3.54 and standard deviation of 0.53 (Strongly Agree). Indicator 6, provides examples to clarify statement obtained the highest mean of 3.64 with the mean of 0.48 (Strongly Agree) followed by indicator 5, Has clear instructions/directions got the mean of 3.60 and standard deviation 0.53 (Strongly agree), indicator 1, helps in setting clear and achievable learning goals got the mean of 3.58 and standard deviation 0.69 (Strongly agree) indicator 2, assists in defining my learning objectives got the mean of 3.39 and standard deviation 0.62 (agree), and indicator 4, is easy to understand got the mean of 3.38 and standard deviation 0.57 (agree). While indicator 3, are helpful in establishing specific milestones to achieve my learning goals got the lowest mean of 3.37 and standard deviation of 0.64 (Agree). This means that most of the respondents perceived the learning materials positively and were able to understand the instructions clearly with the help of examples given in the learning materials.

Table 3 shows the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials as to topics. The indicator of learning topics has an overall mean of 3.43 and standard deviation of 0.61 (agree). It is shown on the table that indicator 3, the key points and arguments are presented in a logical and organized manner got the highest mean of 3.55 and standard deviation of 0.52 (Strongly agree), followed by indicator 2, the main concepts and ideas related to the topic are explained got the mean of 3.49 and standard deviation of 0.63 (agree), indicator 4, examples, anecdotes, or case studies used to effectively illustrate the content got the mean of 3.44 and standard deviation of 0.66 (agree), and indicator 5, recent developments, trends, or advancements related to the topic were discussed got mean of 3.31 and standard deviation of 0.64 (agree).

Table 3. *Perception of the respondents on the Contents of the Learning Materials as to Topics*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The topics of the learning materials</i>			
1. The topic is relevant and significant for the target audience	3.29	0.65	Agree
2. The main concepts and ideas related to the topic are explained	3.49	0.63	Agree
3. The key points and arguments are presented in a logical and organized manner	3.55	0.52	Strongly Agree
4. Examples, anecdotes, or case studies are used to effectively illustrate the content	3.44	0.66	Agree
5. Recent developments, trends, or advancements related to the topic were discussed	3.31	0.64	Agree
Overall	3.43	0.61	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Aside from that, indicator 1, the topic is relevant and significant for the target audience got the lowest mean of 3.29 (agree). The data shows that the respondent of the study finds the key points and arguments in the learning material to be well-presented and organized.

Table 4 reveals the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials in terms of pedagogy. The indicators of learning pedagogy has an overall mean of 3.41 and standard deviation of 0.64 (agree). It is also shown on the table that indicator 2, content are related to real-life situations, relevant and meaningful for students has the highest mean of 3.48 and standard deviation of 0.63 (agree), followed by indicator 6, encourages students to ask questions related to the content with the mean of 3.46 and standard deviation of 0.56 (agree), indicator 5, uses a variety of assessment methods to gauge students' understanding of the content got mean of 3.39 and standard deviation of 0.59 (agree), indicator 4, content encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills through discussions got mean of 3.37 and standard deviation of 0.77 (agree), indicator 1, uses variety of instructional strategies to engage students in the subject matter got mean of 3.36 and standard deviation 0.65 (agree), and indicator 7, updated with the latest research and advancement in the subject area got mean of 3.33 and standard deviation of 0.71 (agree). On the other hand, it is also shown on the table that the lowest mean is indicator number 3 integrated multimedia (e.g., videos, simulations) to enhance content understanding has the mean 3.15 (agree). These data revealed that the respondents were able to understand and relate to the contents of the learning materials when the content were related to real-life situations.

Table 4. Perception of the respondents on the Content of Learning Materials as to Pedagogy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The Pedagogy of learning materials</i>			
1. Uses variety of instructional strategies to engage students in the subject matter.	3.36	0.65	Agree
2. Content are related to real-life situations, making it relevant and meaningful for students.	3.48	0.63	Agree
3. Integrated multimedia (e.g., videos, simulations) to enhance content understanding.	3.15	0.74	Agree
4. Content encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills through discussions.	3.37	0.77	Agree
5. Uses a variety of assessment methods to gauge students' understanding of the content.	3.39	0.59	Agree
6. Encourages students to ask questions related to the content.	3.46	0.56	Agree
7. Updated with the latest research and advancements in the subject area.	3.33	0.71	Agree
Overall	3.41	0.64	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Table 5 shows the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials as to learning evaluation. Based on the table, the evaluation has an overall mean of 3.40 and standard deviation of 0.66 (Agree). Indicator 3, provide opportunities for hands-on exercises or real-world applications has the highest mean of 3.42 and standard deviation of 0.61 (agree) followed by indicator 2, provided opportunities for hands-on exercises or real-world applications got mean of 3.41 and standard deviation of 0.69 (agree).

Table 5. Perception of the respondents on the Contents of the Learning Materials as to Evaluation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The Evaluation of the learning materials</i>			
1. Could often be used for practice and applying what I have learned	3.38	0.67	Agree
2. Provide opportunities for hands-on exercises or real-world applications	3.41	0.69	Agree
3. Are helpful in preparing for my assessments, exams or practical demonstration of knowledge	3.42	0.61	Agree
Overall	3.40	0.66	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

While indicator 1, could often be used for practice and applying what I have learned got the lowest mean of 3.38 and standard deviation of 0.67 (Agree). The statistical data revealed that the respondents were able to use the assessments provided in the learning materials to prepare and practice for their incoming exams or practical demonstrations.

Table 6. Perception of the respondents on the Contents of the Learning Materials as to Reflection

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The reflection of the learning materials</i>			
1. Could be used to reflect on learning progress and understanding the subject	3.43	0.6	Agree
2. Could encouraged me to think critically about what I have learned	3.38	0.663	Agree
3. Are helpful in facilitating self-assessment and identifying areas for improvement in my learning journey	3.45	0.65	Agree
Overall	3.42	0.66	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Table 6 shows the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials as to learning reflection. Based on the table, the learning reflection has an overall mean of 3.42 and standard deviation of 0.66 (Agree). Indicator 3, are helpful in facilitating self-assessment and identifying areas for improvement in my learning journey got the highest mean of 3.45 and standard deviation of 0.65 (Agree), followed by indicator 1, could be used to reflect on my learning progress with the mean of 3.43 and standard deviation of 0.68 (agree) while indicator 2, could encouraged me to think critically about what I have learned got the lowest mean of 3.38 and standard deviation of 0.66 (Agree). The statistical data revealed that the reflection in learning materials were able to help them to reflect and identify the areas that they haven't mastered yet in their learning journey.

Table 7. Perception of the respondents on the Contents of the Learning Materials as to Layout

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The layout of the learning materials</i>			
1. Are appealing to the eyes	3.42	0.65	Agree
2. Are organized	3.55	0.63	Strongly Agree
3. Has appropriate design	3.49	0.60	Agree
4. Has proper spacing	3.53	0.54	Strongly Agree
5. Uses readable and attractive font	3.51	0.58	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.49	0.61	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Table 7 shows the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials as to layout. Based on the table, the layout indicator has an overall mean of 3.49 (Agree). Indicator 2, are organized obtained the highest mean of 3.55 and standard deviation of 0.63 (Strongly Agree), followed by indicator 4, has proper spacing with mean 3.53 and standard deviation of 0.54 (Strongly agree), indicator 5, uses readable and attractive font got mean of 3.51 and standard deviation 0.58 (Strongly agree), and indicator 3, has appropriate design got mean of 3.49 and standard deviation of 0.60 (agree). While indicator 1, are appealing to the eyes got the lowest mean of 3.42 (Agree). This means that the respondents perceived the layout of learning materials positively and in logical order. Though indicator 1 shows a slightly lower mean, the respondents still saw it visually appealing.

Table 8 shows the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials as to adaptable. Based on the table, adaptable has an overall mean of 3.40 and standard deviation of 0.63 (Agree). Indicator 5, cover the key concepts and topics that need to focus obtained the highest mean of 3.52 and standard deviation of 0.65 (Strongly Agree), followed by indicator 4, aligns with the stated learning objective got mean of 3.46 and standard deviation of 0.58 (agree), indicator 9 provides real-time feedback on the learners' performance and indicator 11 provides practical examples that enhance the learners' understanding has the same mean 3.45 and standard deviation 0.66 (agree), indicator 6, keeps the learners engaged and motivated to learn got the mean of 3.42 and standard deviation of 0.71 (agree), indicator 3, provides personalized recommendations for further study got the same mean of indicator 6 with mean of 3.42 but varies with the mean 0.54 (agree), indicator 7, offers interactive elements (quizzes, simulations) that enhances learners' engagement got mean of 3.40 and standard deviation of 0.66 (agree), indicator 8, challenges learners to think critically and apply knowledge got the mean of 3.35 and standard deviation of 0.86 (agree) indicator 2, adjusts its difficulty level based on the learners performance progress got mean of 3.33 and standard deviation 0.69 (agree), and indicator 10, easy to navigate and use got the mean of 3.31 and standard deviation of 0.57 (Agree) while indicator 1, tailors the content to my individual learning needs got the lowest mean 3.35 and standard deviation of 0.64 (agree). The data revealed that the developed learning material were adaptable to learners as its content is tailored for the individual needs of the learners.

Table 8. Perception of the respondents on the Contents of the Learning Materials as to Adaptable

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The adaptability of learning materials</i>			
1. Tailors the content to my individual learning needs.	3.25	0.64	Agree
2. Adjusts its difficulty level based on the learners performance and progress.	3.33	0.69	Agree
3. Provides personalized recommendations for further study.	3.42	0.54	Agree
4. Aligns with the stated learning objectives.	3.46	0.58	Agree
5. Cover the key concepts and topics that need to focus.	3.52	0.65	Strongly Agree
6. Keeps the learners engaged and motivated to learn.	3.42	0.71	Agree
7. Offers interactive elements (quizzes simulations) that enhances learners' engagement.	3.40	0.66	Agree
8. Challenges learners to think critically and apply knowledge.	3.35	0.68	Agree
9. Provides real-time feedback on learners' performance.	3.45	0.66	Agree
10. Easy to navigate and use.	3.31	0.57	Agree
11. Provides practical examples that enhance the learners' understanding.	3.45	0.66	Agree
Overall	3.40	0.63	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Table 9 shows the perception of the respondents on the Contents of the learning materials as to user-friendliness. Based on the table, it has an overall mean of 3.46 and standard deviation of 0.57 (Agree). Indicator 5, Images, examples and other elements enhances the learning experience obtained the highest mean of 3.56 and standard deviation of 0.61 (Strongly Agree), followed by indicator 2, language used in the learning material is clear and easily understandable got the mean of 3.46 and standard deviation of 0.54 (agree), indicator 3, technical terms are explained or defined properly got mean of 3.45 and standard deviation of 0.54 (agree), and indicator 1, is well-organized and easy to follow got the mean of 3.44 and standard deviation of 0.58 (agree). While indicator 4, Interactive elements are easy to identify and use got the lowest mean of 3.39 and standard deviation of 0.57 (Agree). This means that the materials were user friendly and the respondents able to understand the language used. Though indicator 4 has a slightly lower mean than the rests it still suggests that the material is generally easy to identify and use.

Table 9. Perception of the respondents on the Contents of the Learning Materials as to User Friendliness

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
<i>The user friendliness of learning materials</i>			
1. Is well-organized and easy to follow.	3.44	0.58	Agree
2. Language used in the learning material is clear and easily understandable.	3.46	0.54	Agree
3. Technical terms are explained or defined appropriately.	3.45	0.54	Agree
4. Interactive elements are easy to identify and use.	3.39	0.57	Agree
5. Images, examples and other elements enhances the learning experience.	3.56	0.6	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.46	0.57	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Table 10 shows the summary of the Perception of Respondents on the Components of Learning Materials. Based on the table the average mean on contents were 3.44 while the standard deviation were 0.61 (Agree), the standard deviation on Layout is 3.49 with

mean of 0.61 (Agree), the mean on Adaptive is 3.40 with standard deviation of 0.63 (Agree) and the mean on user-friendliness is 3.46 with the standard deviation of 0.57 (Agree). The objectives of learning materials had a mean rating of 3.54 and standard deviation of 0.53 with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree; topics had mean of 3.43, standard deviation of 0.61 and verbal interpretation of agree; pedagogy has the mean of 3.41, standard deviation of 0.61 and verbal interpretation of agree; evaluation has the mean of 3.40, standard deviation of 0.66 and verbal interpretation of agree; and Reflection got the mean of 3.42, standard deviation of 0.66 and verbal interpretation of agree. It's over all mean rating is 3.41 and standard deviation of 0.61 with over all verbal interpretation of agree.

Table 10. Summary of Perception of Respondents on the Components of Learning Materials

Components of Learning Materials	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretations
1. Contents			
• Objectives	3.54	0.53	Strongly Agree
• Topics	3.43	0.61	Agree
• Pedagogy	3.41	0.61	Agree
• Evaluation	3.40	0.66	Agree
• Reflection	3.42	0.66	Agree
Overall	3.44	0.61	Agree
2. Layout	3.49	0.61	Agree
3. Adaptive	3.40	0.63	Agree
4. User Friendliness	3.46	0.57	Agree
Overall	3.41	0.61	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.5-4.0 (Strongly Agree)

Additionally, layout got the mean rating of 3.49, standard deviation of 0.61 and verbal interpretation of agree, adaptive got the mean rating of 3.40, standard deviation of 0.63 and verbal interpretation of agree and user friendliness was rated with a mean of 3.46 and standard deviation of 0.57 and verbal interpretation of agree. The overall perception of the respondents on all components of learning material got the mean of 3.41, standard deviation of 0.57 and verbal interpretation of agree.

This means that the respondents of the study were approved on the components of the developed learning material as it meets their needs and expectations that may contribute to a positive learning experience.

Table 11. Distribution of Respondents Scores in Developing a Business Plan

Scores	Rating	Frequency	Percentage	Verbal Interpretations
76-90	90 and Above	1	1.05	Excellent
57-75	85-89	33	34.74	Very Good
35-56	80-84	61	64.21	Good
19-33	75-79			Fair
0-18	70-74			Poor
Total		95	100	

Legend: 70-74- poor, 75-79-Fair, 80-84- Good, 85-89-Very good, 90and above Excellent

Table 11 shows the distribution of respondent's scores in developing business plan. Based on the table, 1 or (1.05%) got the rating of 90 and above and verbal interpretation of excellent, 33 (34.74%) got the rating of 85-89 and a verbal interpretation of very good, while 61 (64.21%) with verbal interpretations of good is the respondents scores in developing a business plan. The statistical data shows that majority of the respondents were good in developing business plan, followed by significant portion rated as very good and a smaller percentage that are excellent. This means that even though most of the respondents shows competency in developing business plan they are still in need for improvement to attain very good and excellent.

Table 12. Distribution of Respondents Scores in Oral Presentation

Scores	Rating	Frequency	Percentage	Verbal Interpretations
Above 24	90 and above	57	60	Excellent
19-24	85-89	34	35.8	Very Good
13-18	80-84	3	3.15	Good
7-12	75-79	1	1.05	Fair
0-6	70-74			Poor
Total		95	100	

Legend: 70-74- poor, 75-79-Fair, 80-84- Good, 85-89-Very good, 90and above Excellent

Table 12 shows the distribution of respondent's scores in oral presentation. Based on the table, 57 or (60%) of the respondents were excellent in oral presentation, 34 (35.8%) is very good, 3 (3.15%) is good and 1 or (1.05%) of the learners got the fair verbal interpretations in Oral Presentations. The statistical data shows that majority of the respondents were excellent in oral presentations followed by a significant portion rated as very good, a small percentage that rated as good and an even smaller portion rated as fair. This means that even though most of them excelled in oral presentations and proficiency in communication there are still individuals

that need improvement.

Table 13 presents the significant relationships of the respondents' perception on the components of learning materials and learning competencies in Entrepreneurship.

The obtained r-values as indicated for each variables tested in this study, specifically on the components of learning materials and its association to the learning competency of the learners as to business planning, clearly denotes a moderate to high correlation with the r-values ranging from 0.312- 0.506 (moderate) to 0.637 (high).

Table 13. *Significant relationship of the components of learning Materials and Learning Competencies in Entrepreneurship*

<i>Components of Learning Materials</i>	<i>Learning Competencies</i>	
	<i>Business Plan</i>	<i>Oral Presentation</i>
• Contents		
Objectives	.312**	.075
Topics	.388**	.286**
Pedagogy	.492**	.236**
Evaluation	.330**	.141
Learning Reflection	.426**	.166
• Layout	.501**	.221*
• Adaptability	.506**	.303**
• User-Friendliness	.637**	.273**

**Correlation is significant at the level 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the level 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It should be noted that among the components of learning materials user friendliness is the sole variable that is highly correlated to the respondents' competencies in business planning and all the rest of the variables registered a moderate association. In addition, a user-friendly material that are easy to navigate and comprehend minimizes the cognitive load on the learners and they could be more focused on learning how to do the tasks written of the learning materials rather than figuring out how to utilize them. Park and Kim (2021) assert that user-friendly design is essential for online learning materials since it fosters students' development of stronger business planning skills. By raising student performance and satisfaction, teachers may establish more effective and engaging learning environments by making their resources more accessible and user-friendly.

However test of significant relationships between the respondents' performance in oral presentation and their perception in objectives as Components of Learning Materials revealed no significant association as reflected in the r-value of 0 .075. Moreover, the same insignificant relationship existed on contents of learning materials as to its evaluation (r- .144) and learning reflection (r- .166) and the respondents' learning competency with regards to oral presentation. Nevertheless, a low correlation existed between components of learning materials as to topics and pedagogy and respondents' competency in oral presentation with the r- values 0.286** and 0.236** respectively. The same low relationship were registered between the learning materials' layout (0.221*), Adaptable (0.303**), User-Friendliness (0.273**) and respondents' competency in oral presentation This result might have been affected by different factors such as nature of oral presentation, complexity of learning outcomes etc. In that case, the teacher might focus on the design of the curriculum and enhancing the learning materials. This result is evident in the study conducted by Park and Kim (2021) stating that user-friendly design is essential for online learning materials since it fosters students' development of stronger business planning skills.

By raising student performance and satisfaction, teachers may establish more effective and engaging learning environments by making their resources more accessible and user-friendly.

Generally, the findings revealed that there is low relationship between the respondents' performance in oral presentation and their perception in Components of Learning Materials while moderate to high correlation existed between the respondents' perception on the learning materials and their competencies in developing a business plan.

This findings generally connote that while all the components of learning materials are related to the learning competencies in entrepreneurship in term of business planning, they do not have a distinct impact on enhancing the respondent's oral presentation skills specifically the content of the learning materials in terms of objectives, evaluation and learning reflection.

Conclusions

In conclusion based on the results, while the components of learning materials demonstrate a significant relationship with the specified learning competency among respondent in developing Business Plan, the stated null hypothesis that components of learning materials do not significantly relate to the development of the targeted competencies among grade 9 entrepreneurship students is not sustained.

While the components of the developed learning materials demonstrated a combination of both insignificant and significant relationship on oral presentations skills of the respondents, the hypothesis in this regard is partially accepted.

Based on the result of the study, the researcher arrived at the following recommendations:

Teachers may be encouraged to continue developing learning materials in different competencies of Entrepreneurship 9 which will help the learners to understand the lesson easily, they may also prioritize the making learning material that is more user-friendly that will help the learners to engage effectively and develop learning materials that will help the learners to improve oral presentation skills.

Future researchers may conduct further investigation to understand the underlying factors contributing to the gap between components of learning materials and learning competencies and develop more effective instructional strategies tailored to enhance the targeted competencies and may also investigate the potential mediating factors that may influence the relationship between components of learning materials and learning competencies.

References

Department of Education. (2020). DEped Order No. 12, s. 2020: Guidelines on the Selection and Use of Learning Resources for the K to 12 Basic Education Program. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/DO_s2020_018.pdf

Department of Education (2021). Entrepreneurship. Alternative Delivery Mode Quarter 1 - Module 1, Introduction to Entrepreneurship, Second Edition.

Department of Education (2013). Republic Act 10533 Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 <https://depedph.com/republic-act-10533-enhanced-basic-education-act/#google>

Department of Education (2023). Policy Guidelines for Supplementary Instructional Materials Adoption and Use in Public Elementary and Secondary Schools <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2023/09/19/september-19-2023-do-024-s-2023-guidelines-on-the-provision-of-supplementary-learning-resources-for-public-school-libraries-and-library-hubs/>

Katzawai, R., Sandaran, S. C., Haidari, M. (2019). An Evaluation of Sub Skills (Vocabulary, Grammar and Pronunciation) in the Grade 9 English Textbook of Afghan Secondary School, <https://scite.ai/reports/an-evaluation-of-sub-skills-vocabulary-eP0w1j6>

Park, S., & Kim, L. (2021). Effects of User-Friendly Learning Materials on Student Performance and Satisfaction in Online Business Education. *Journal of Educational Technology and Society*, 45-58

Richards, J. C. (2014). *Reflective teaching in second language classrooms*. Cambridge University Press.

Simonson, M., Smaldino, S., Albright, M., & Zvacek, S. (2012). *Teaching and learning at a distance: Foundations of distance education* (5th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson.

Solberg, V.S., Wills, J., Redmon, K. & Skaff, L. (2014). *Use of Individualized Learning Plans: A Promising Practice for Driving College and Career Efforts*. National Collaborative on Workforce and Disability for Youth, Institute for Educational Leadership.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Janen C. Galang

Laguna State Polytechnic University – Philippines